

ETHNICS

△ABOUT △I AND △DATA

In education and lifelong learning

USE CASE

AI to support Communication

A teacher uses Dall-E (an image generation system) and Canva (freemium versions) to generate a presentation for an Open Day about the University Degree. In creating some of the images, she realizes that educators and nurses refer to women, smiling and caring. The representations of engineers, surgeons and programmers always refer to males.

By the end of the course, she uses students' photos taken throughout the year of activities conducted by her students. The material will be further used in the University's Instagram account to promote new enrollments to the degree.

Have you ever found yourself in a similar situation?

What are your feelings about this?

Let us consider the following ethical criteria

#CARD III - DIVERSITY, NON-DISCRIMINATION AND EQUITY

#CARD V - DATA CONFIDENTIALITY AND GOVERNANCE

What are the problems in this practice?

What would be an “ethical” approach?

Future of AI in HE classrooms (and beyond): Your Reflections

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